

FLUTTER ANALYSIS OF LAST STAGE STEAM TURBINE WITH UNIFORM AND NON-UNIFORM PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION BEHIND ROTOR BLADES

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ABSTRACT

Cracks were found in the roots and leading edges of LP last stage steam turbine rotor blades. Tip-timing measurements showed high vibration amplitudes in nominal working conditions.

The aim of this paper is to analyse last stage rotor blade flutter in nominal and non-nominal working conditions, taking into account unsteady flow caused by the exhaust hood, which generates non-uniform pressure distribution behind the rotor blades.

In literature, flutter analyses have been done for last stage LP steam turbine blades with uniform pressure distribution behind the rotor blades [1], [2], [4] and [5]. This paper, however, considers non-uniform pressures behind last-stage rotor blades in nominal and non-nominal regimes to show the significance of the exhaust hood in flutter analysis.

Keywords: flutter, steam turbine, last LP stage

1. INTRODUCTION

Cracks were found in the roots and leading edges of LP last stage steam turbine rotor blades. Tip-timing measurements showed high vibration amplitudes in nominal working conditions.

The aim of this paper is to analyze last stage rotor blade flutter in nominal and non-nominal working conditions, taking into account unsteady flow caused by the exhaust hood, which generates non-uniform pressure distribution behind the rotor blades.

In literature, flutter analyses have been done of last stage LP steam turbine blades with uniform pressure distribution behind the rotor blades [1], [2], [4] and [5]. This paper, however, considers non-uniform pressures behind last-stage rotor blades in nominal and non-nominal regimes to show the significance of the exhaust hood in flutter analysis taken from [6].

2. METHOD

Flutter in the last stage of an LP steam turbine was analysed in [7] assuming the pressure distribution behind the rotor blades was uniform. However, the exhaust hood generates non-symmetrical pressure distribution behind the rotor blades. Therefore, in this paper, flutter is analyzed, taking into account non-symmetrical pressure distribution for five working regimes (Fig. 1), where p_{LP} is pressure in the rotor blade inlet, and p_k is the condenser pressure.

FIGURE 1: Five working regimes

A 3D RANS solver with a modified Baldwin and Lomax algebraic eddy viscous turbulence model was used to calculate unsteady viscous flow through an LP last stage eddy viscous turbulence model. The flow equations were written for a three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system fixed to a rotating blade row. The numerical method used the explicit finite-volume Godunov's type second-order by time and coordinates difference scheme with a moving H-O structured grid. The structure analysis used the modal approach and a 3D finite element blade model.

Hybrid H-H and O-O grids were used for each rotor passage. During the calculations, the outer H-grid of the rotor remained stationary, while the inner O-grid or H-grid was rebuilt in each iteration, in accordance with blade motion. To validate the numerical viscous code, the numerical results were compared with data measured for the 11th International Standard Configuration [8].

The blade vibration formulation was based on a modal approach [2, 3]. The dynamic model of the oscillating blade in linearized formulation was governed by the matrix equation:

$$M \ddot{u} + C \dot{u} + K u = F, \quad (1)$$

where: M , C , and K are the mass, mechanical damping and stiffness matrices of the blade, respectively; u is the blade displacement; F is the unsteady aerodynamic forces vector.

The first step of the modal approach involved solving the problem of the natural mode shapes and eigenvalues without damping and in a vacuum. Thus the displacement of each blade could be written as a linear combination of the first N modes shapes with the modal coefficients depending on time:

$$u = Uq = \sum_{i=1}^N U_i q_i \quad (2)$$

where: U_i is the displacement vector corresponding to the i -th mode shape, and q_i is the modal coefficient of the i -th mode. Taking into account equation (1) and the orthogonality of the mode shapes, the dynamic model of the oscillating blade was reduced to a set of independent differential equations relative to modal coefficients of natural modes ([2]):

$$\ddot{q}_i + 2h_i \dot{q}_i + \omega_i^2 q_i = \lambda_i, \quad (3)$$

where: h_i is the mechanical damping of the i -th mode coefficient; ω_i is the natural i -th mode frequency; λ_i the modal force relative to i -th mode displacement, calculated at every iteration with the use of an instantaneous pressure field on the blade surface ([2]):

$$\lambda_i = \frac{\sigma \iint p \bar{U}_i \cdot \bar{n}^\circ d\sigma}{\iiint_v \rho \bar{U}_i^2 dv}. \quad (4)$$

where: p is the pressure along the blade surface.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numerical calculations were carried out for steam turbine LP last stage rotor blades. The calculations were performed for harmonic oscillations of the blade row according to natural modes with the same amplitude and inter-blade phase angle (IBPA), and for five regimes. Fig. 1 presents static pressure distribution behind the rotor blades for regime 1.

FIGURE 2: STATIC PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION BEHIND THE ROTOR BLADES FOR REGIME 1

The non-uniform pressure distributions behind the rotor blades in regime 1 (Fig.2) were taken from full annulus stator, rotor blade and exhaust hood unsteady flow calculations [6].

The wet steam was modelled using the polytropic index $k=1.11$. The aeroelastic behaviour of the vibrating blade row was defined by the aerodamping coefficient D , which was equal to the negative work coefficient performed during one cycle of oscillations. The negative values of D correspond to the transfer of mean flow energy to the blade (self-excitation). The positive values correspond to the dissipation of oscillating blade energy to the flow (aerodamping).

Regime 1

The aerodamping coefficient of a rotor blade at different interblade phase angles (IBPA) for the viscous code and 1st mode

regime 1 (Fig. 1) showed that flutter does not appear for non-symmetrical blade distribution behind the rotor blades (Fig. 3a).

FIGURE 3A: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 1

FIGURE 3B: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT ALONG BLADE LENGTH OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 1, IBPA=-90 DEG

FIGURE 3C: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT ALONG BLADE LENGTH OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 1 (FOR IBPA =-90, 0, 90, 180 DEG)

Figure 3b, 3c presents the aerodamping coefficient along the blade length for the 1st mode, regime 1 and various IBPA. The averaged aerodamping coefficient is positive for most IBPA, but it is negative in certain parts along the blade length. For IBPA =-90 deg, the flutter appears in the region of 0.9 to 1 of the blade length.

In case the uniform pressure distribution behind the rotor blade, flutter appears in the 1st mode shape (Fig. 4) with an IBPA from -100 deg. to -80 deg.

Figure 4: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, UNIFORM PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION

Figs 3a and 4 showed that flutter appeared in the 1st mode for uniform pressure distribution, but did not appear for non-uniform pressure distribution behind the rotor blades.

Regime 2

The aerodamping coefficient of a rotor blade at various interblade phase angles (IBPA) for the viscous code and the 1st mode regime 2 (Fig. 1) shows that flutter does not appear (Figure 5a).

The static pressure before the low-pressure part of an LP steam turbine (p_{LP} Fig. 1) is similar for regimes 1 and 2, but in 2 the condenser pressure (p_k Fig. 1) is higher. In this case, the rise pressure prevents flutter from appearing.

Figure 5A: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 2

Figure 6: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 3

Figure 5B: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT ALONG BLADE LENGTH OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 2, IBPA=0,-90,90,180 DEG

Figure 5b presents the aerodamping coefficient along the blade length for the 1st mode, regime 2 and various IBPA. The averaged aerodamping coefficient is positive for most IBPA, but it is negative in certain parts along the blade length. For IBPA=0, 90 and -90 deg, the flutter appears in the region of 0.4 to 0.9 of the blade length, and for IBPA= 180 deg in the region of 0.4 to 0.8.

Regime 3

The aerodamping coefficient of a rotor blade at different interblade phase angles (IBPA) for the viscous code, regime 3 and the 1st mode show that flutter does not appear (Figure 6).

Figure 7: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 3, IBPA=90 DEG

Figure 8: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT ALONG BLADE LENGTH OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 3, IBPA=0, -90, 90, 180 DEG

Figure 7 presents the aerodamping coefficient along the blade length for the 1st mode and IBPA =90 deg. The average aerodamping coefficient is positive. The flutter appears locally, from 0.2 to 0.81 of the blade length, for IBPA= -90 deg in the region of 0.95 to 1 and 0.3 to 0.4 and for IBPA 180 deg it appeared in the region of 0.2 to 0.5 (Fig. 8).

In regime 3, the static pressure before the low pressure part of the turbine (p_{LP} Fig. 1) is lower than in regime 2, and the condenser pressure (p_k Fig. 1) is also lower. In regime 3, flutter does not appear.

Regime 4

The aerodamping coefficient of a rotor blade at different interblade phase angles (IBPA) for the viscous code, 1st mode and regime 4 (Fig. 1) shows that flutter appears at -90 deg and 90 deg IBPA (Figure 9).

Figure 9: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 4, IBPA=-90 DEG

Figure 10: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 4, IBPA=-90 DEG

Figure 11: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT ALONG BLADE LENGTH OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 4, IBPA=0, -90, 90, 180 DEG

Figures 10 and 11 present the aerodamping coefficient along the blade length for the 1st mode and various IBPA. In the case of IBPA=-90 deg, the flutter appears in the region of 0.3 to 1 of the blade length and for IBPA=90 deg, in the region of 0.7 to 1. The average aerodamping coefficient is negative. Flutter also appears in the case of uniform pressured distribution behind the rotor blades.

The static pressure before the low-pressure part of an LP steam turbine (p_{LP} Fig. 1) is similar for regimes 4 and 3, but in 3, the condenser pressure (p_k Fig. 1) is higher. Here, the rise of condenser pressure and lower pressure p_{LP} in comparison with regimes 1 and 2 causes flutter to appear.

Regime 5

The aerodamping coefficient of a rotor blade at different interblade phase angles (IBPA) for the viscous code, regime 5 (Fig. 1) and the 1st mode show that flutter appears at a 90 deg IBPA (Fig. 12a). Figures 12a and 13 present the aerodamping coefficient along the blade length for the 1st mode and various IBPA. In the case of IBPA=90 deg, flutter appears in the region of 0.6 to 0.9 of the blade length.

Figure 12A: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 5

Figure 12B: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 5, IBPA=-90 DEG

Figure 13: AERODAMPING COEFFICIENT ALONG BLADE LENGTH OF THE 1ST BLADE MODE, REGIME 5, IBPA=0, -90, 90, 180 DEG

In Figures 12a and 12b, the average aerodamping coefficient is negative. In the case of 0, 180 and -90 IBPA, the aerodamping coefficient is positive along the blade length (Fig. 13), although for IBPA=-90 deg and 0 there are small areas where the averaged aerodamping coefficient is negative. Flutter also appears for uniform pressure distribution the rotor blades. The static pressure before the low-pressure part of a LP steam turbine (p_{LP} Fig. 1) and the condenser pressure are smaller in regime 5 than in regimes 3, 4, 2 and 1. Therefore flow unsteadiness is also higher, which causes flutter to appear.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, the simultaneous time domain method and the modal superposition method were used to determine the aeroelastic stability of last stage LP steam turbine blades in various working conditions. The influence of the natural modes on aeroelastic blade behaviour was numerically analysed with nonsymmetrical pressure distribution behind the rotor blades for various non-nominal regimes.

Numerical calculations were performed for harmonic blade row oscillations in the 1st mode with the same amplitude and various interblade phase angles (IBPA) using 3D viscous flow codes. These show that flutter appears in the 1st mode in regime 1 for IBPA = -90 and uniform pressure distribution, but not for non-uniform pressure distribution. Flutter also appears in regime 4 for IBPA = -90 deg and 90 deg and regime 5 at IBPA = 90 deg for non-uniform and uniform pressure distribution. The aerodamping coefficient sign, which changes along the blade length is dependent on the IBPA. It is negative in one part of the blade, while in another part it is positive. These areas change, depending on the IBPA and regime. This paper shows the significance of the exhaust hood in flutter analysis.

Decreasing static pressure before the low pressure part of a LP steam turbine (p_{LP} see Fig. 1) and decreasing condenser pressure causes higher flow unsteadiness and flutter.

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